

**COMPETENCY TRAINING NEEDS OF BUSINESS EDUCATION LECTURERS ON THE
USAGE OF LESSON PLANNING AND LESSON PRESENTATION SOFTWARE
APPLICATIONS FOR INSTRUCTIONS: A PILOT STUDY**

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Abstract

The pilot study aimed at determining the competency training needs of business education lecturers on the usage of lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications for instructional delivery. The study was carried out at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprises of 12 business education lecturers in the university. The entire population was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated by two experts from the department of vocational education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola. The reliability (internal consistency) of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha; a coefficient of 0.83 and 0.87 for lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications respectively were found. The researcher through a research assistant administered the instrument to the respondents manually. A total of 12 questionnaires were administered but only 11 were retrieved. The research questions were analysed using mean weighted discrepancy score (MWDS) while hypotheses were analysed using one-way analysis of variance statistics. The finding of the study among others revealed that business education lecturers need training in the usage of both lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications for instructional delivery. It was also found that significant difference exists among business education lecturers who specialized in accounting, marketing and office technology management on their training needs in the use of lesson planning software application but no significant difference exists on their training needs in the use of lesson presentation software application among them. The study recommended that the instrument's sub-scales for measuring the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications should be used for the main study since they were found to be reliable and acceptable.

Keywords: Training Needs, Lesson Planning, Lesson Presentation, Software Applications

Introduction

The relevance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in instructional delivery cannot be overemphasized most especially in emerging nations such as Nigeria. Among the ICT resources include software applications. There are various software applications out there that can aid instructional delivery and have the potentials of influencing students' learning experiences (Asri, 2017). In the last decade, ICT has influenced innovations in lecturers' instructional delivery practice (Janssen et al., 2019) most especially through the use of

software applications. In view of this, there is need for university lecturers to effectively utilize these software applications in their instructional delivery most especially lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications.

Preparation of lesson plan is among the relevant practices toward improvement of the quality of instructions since effective planning of the lesson assists teachers to improve instructional delivery. Lesson planning is a core activity of professional teachers (Konig et al., 2020) and also a precondition for effective instructional delivery (Strickroth, 2019). In support of this, Stella as cited by Halala and Seni (2022) argued that the quality of instruction is determined by instructors' preparation and effective use of lesson plans. Similarly, Innocent (2021) asserts that among the benefits of effective lesson planning include improving instructions and consequently improving the students' academic performance. Lesson planning did not only serve as a guide to the teachers in instructional delivery, but also assists them on how learners' abilities are to be distributed in classroom (Basturk et al., 2022). Today, lesson plans were developed using software applications which simplifies the complex process of planning the lesson thereby facilitating instructional delivery (Strickroth, 2019). Lesson planning software applications are packages used for the design and preparation of lesson plans. Example of these applications include: Planner, Lesson Plan Maker, PlanbookEdu, MyLessonPlanner, Planboard, Lesson Planner Advanced, StarPlanIt, Coach Diary, Common Curriculum, Plan4Me, Lesson Planning System (LPS), Fun 5 Plans, Instructional Planning Assistant System (IPAS), Support for Teachers Enhancing Performance in Schools (STEPS), Eduwiki (EW), Inquiry in Motion Dynamic Lesson Planning Tool (IIM), Smart Lesson Planning System (SLP), The Learning Designer (LDSE), Task Stream (TS), Phoebe Pedagogic Planner (Ph) and many more (Monett & Weishaar, 2015; Common Sense Media, 2020; Strickroth, 2019).

Lesson presentation is a systematic process lecturers follow in executing the instructional steps in delivering instructions to students. These steps can be followed through traditional face-to-face method or through the use of technology such as lesson presentation software applications. Lesson presentation software applications are the application software packages that create multimedia stacks of cards or screens which can effectively display or present a lesson in a sequential manner. Example of these include: MS PowerPoint, Prezi, HyperCard, Keynote, Digital Chisel, HyperStudio, Google Slide, Ludus, Customshow, Emaze, Director, Flash, SuperCard, Corel Envoy, Producer, Apple Works, Xerte and many more (Harris, 2011; Ukeh et al., 2020). Lesson presentation software applications can assist teachers present their course contents using tables, graphs, maps and animations thereby facilitating instructional delivery (Asri, 2017). Previous research studies have found that students taught using lesson presentation software applications performed better than those taught using conventional method (Ukeh et al., 2020). Similarly, it was empirically established that using lesson presentation software applications in instructional delivery was reported to have improved teacher-students' interaction and increased students understanding (Motamedi, 2015). Based on the potentials of lesson presentation software applications, Ukeh et al. (2020) recommended their utilization in instructional delivery to improve the students' performance.

However, there are various studies conducted that are relevant to this study; Onajite and Aina (2017) reported that business education lecturers in colleges of education need training in the preparation of lesson plans using computer system and in using PowerPoint presentation software; Timya et al., (2019) concluded that office technology management (OTM) lecturers in polytechnics need training in the use of interactive multimedia software

for instructions; Duktur (2019) also reported that business education undergraduate students need training in the use of PowerPoint presentation software; similarly, Beaulieu and Poyo (2021) asserted that educators need training in the application of principle of redundancy and coherence in their electronic slide presentation; in the same vein, Hassan and Mirza (2021) argued that 94 percent of teachers need training to support the utilization of ICTs in instructional delivery; also, Ardic and Ciftci (2019) stated that teachers need training in the use of ITCs; moreover, Anaza (2019) concluded that student-teachers in colleges of education need training in the use of software applications; more so, Rizal et al., (2019) reported that preservice science teachers need training in content creation including electronic presentation using presentation software applications; another findings of the study carried out by Dlamini and Mbatha (2018) indicated among others that teachers need professional development (training) in the use of ICT in teaching. Based the previous studies, the evidence of training needs in the use of lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications among business education lecturers in universities is yet to be known to the best of the researchers' knowledge as at the time of reporting this study.

According to the International Society for Technology in Education (2017), one of the standards developed to assist teachers to enhance students' learning include continuous improvement of teachers' practice through learning with and from others as well as exploring proven practices that influences technology to enhance students' learning. This standard can best be achieved through training and professional development of teachers, in order to have a successful training of teachers, there is need to ascertain the relevant competency training needs of the teachers because Ghufli (2014) argued that conducting training without identifying the training needs of the trainees will end of becoming waste of time and scarce resources, to this end, this study intends to determine the competency training needs of business education lecturers on the use of lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria as a pilot study with the view to assisting the researchers to make necessary improvements to the major study.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What are the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson planning software applications?
- ii. What are the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson presentation software applications?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson planning software applications among business education lecturers based on their specialization.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson presentation software applications among business education lecturers based on their specialization.

Materials and Methods

The area of the study was Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprises of 12 business education lecturers in the university. The entire population was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed based on the Borich (1980) need assessment model modified by McKim (2013) as indicated in Figure 1. The instrument was validated by two experts from the department of vocational education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola. The reliability (internal consistency) of the instrument was determined using Cronbach’s alpha, a coefficient of 0.83 and 0.87 for sub-scales of lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications respectively were found. The researcher together with one research assistant administered the instrument to the respondents manually. A total of 12 questionnaires were administered to the respondents but only 11 were retrieved. The two research questions were analyzed using mean weighted discrepancy score (MWDS) using an Excel-Based MWDS Calculator (Version 1.4) developed by Mckim and Saucier (2011), while the hypotheses were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance statistics with the aid of IBM-SPSS software (Version 25). The decision rule for analyzing the research questions is that any positive MWDS was interpreted and considered “training needed” (TN) while a zero or negative MWDS was interpreted and considered “training not needed” (TNN).

Figure 1: A Modified Borich’s Needs Assessment Model

Competencies:	Importance of Competency					Ability to Perform				
	No Importance	Below Average Importance	Average Importance	Above Average Importance	Utmost Importance	No Ability	Below Average Ability	Average Ability	Above Average Ability	Exceptional Ability
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
1. Logging/signing in	<input type="checkbox"/>									
2. Creating lesson	<input type="checkbox"/>									

(Source: Mckim, 2013).

Results of the Study

The results of the study were presented based on the research questions and their corresponding hypotheses.

Research Question One: What are the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson planning software applications?

Table 1: Result of the Competency Training Needs of Business Education Lecturers on the use of Lesson Planning Software Applications

S/N	Competencies	MWDS	Decision
1.	Logging/signing in	-2.14	TNN
2.	Setting date/Creating or switching of school year	0.00	TNN
3.	Adding class set up and schedule	-0.39	TNN
4.	Editing class set up and schedule	4.26	TN
5.	Importing events	4.62	TN
6.	Creating lessons	2.58	TN
7.	Editing lessons	3.72	TN
8.	Adding home work	2.98	TN
9.	Adding notes and events	1.83	TN
10.	Adjusting your lesson	4.26	TN
11.	Adjusting events and ‘no school days’	4.56	TN
12.	Sharing lessons with other teachers	2.43	TN
13.	Applying standards and standards reporting	3.91	TN
14.	Navigating your lesson plans	-0.79	TNN
15.	Printing and saving lesson plans	-0.40	TNN
	Cumulative MWDS	2.10	TN

(Source: Field Study, 2022)

KEY: TN = Training Needed, TNN = Training Not Needed

As presented in Table 1, ten (10) out of the fifteen (15) competency items for lesson planning software application (LP) show a positive MWDSs indicting that training is needed (TN) on those competency items while five (5) of the competency items show either zero or negative MWDSs indicating that training is not needed (TNN) on those competency items which are LP 1, LP 2, LP 3, LP 14 and LP 15. The overall MWDS was 2.10 indicating training is needed among business education lecturers in the usage of lesson planning software application.

Research Question Two: What are the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson presentation software applications?

Table 2: Result of the Competency Training Needs of Business Education Lecturers on the usage of Lesson Presentation Software Applications

S/N	Competencies	MWDS	Decision
1.	Creating a new presentation slides	-0.66	TNN
2.	Adding and editing presentation slides	3.64	TN
3.	Rearranging presentation slides	0.00	TNN
4.	Creating presentation views	-2.18	TNN
5.	Creating and adding frames	2.08	TN
6.	Setting backgrounds	-1.04	TNN
7.	Formatting text font, size and colour	2.43	TN
8.	Creating and re-ordering new paths	5.21	TN
9.	Formatting line spacing, borders and shades	5.33	TN
10.	Adding and editing pictures	-1.45	TNN
11.	Formatting added pictures	4.71	TN
12.	Adding and editing shapes	5.58	TN
13.	Formatting added shapes	-1.09	TNN
14.	Inserting a screenshot	5.90	TN
15.	Grouping and ungrouping objects	3.45	TN
16.	Adding audio and video	4.26	TN
17.	Adding and formatting tables and charts	4.51	TN
18.	Adding and previewing animations	2.08	TN
19.	Using the categories template	-0.73	TNN
20.	Broadcasting a slideshow	-1.39	TNN
Cumulative MWDS		2.03	TN

(Source: Field Study, 2022)

As indicated in Table 2, twelve (10) out of the twenty (20) competency items for lesson presentation software application (LPS) show a positive MWDSs indicating that training is needed (TN) on those competency items while eight (8) of the competency items show either zero or negative MWDSs indicating that training is not needed (TNN) on those competency items which are LPS 1, LPS 3, LPS 4, LPS 6, LPS 10, LPS 13, LPS 19 and LPS 20. The overall MWDS was 2.03 indicating that training is needed among business education lecturers in the usage of lesson presentation software application.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson planning software applications among business education lecturers based on their specialization.

Table 3: One-way ANOVA for Mean Difference among Business Education Lecturers on the Competency Training Needs in the usage of Lesson Planning Software Applications

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	2.103	2	1.052	5.975	.026	Reject
Within Groups	1.408	8	.176			
Total	3.511	10				

(Source: Field Study, 2022)

As indicated in Table 3, the result of the ANOVA shows that the p-value (0.03) is less than the alpha value (0.05), therefore, the null hypotheses one is hereby rejected and the alternative hypothesis upheld, this means that significant difference exists on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson planning software applications among business education lecturers who specialized in accounting, marketing and office technology management.

Table 4: Result of Post Hoc Tests (Multiple Comparisons) for Hypothesis One

(I) Specialization	(J) Specialization	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Accounting	Marketing	-1.21333*	.35100	.021	-2.2163	-.2104
	OTM	-.34667	.28142	.469	-1.1508	.4575
Marketing	Accounting	1.21333*	.35100	.021	.2104	2.2163
	OTM	.86667	.36332	.100	-.1715	1.9048
OTM	Accounting	.34667	.28142	.469	-.4575	1.1508
	Marketing	-.86667	.36332	.100	-1.9048	.1715

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

(Source: Field Study, 2022)

As revealed in Table 4, only lecturers who specialized in accounting and marketing significantly differ in their competency training needs in the usage of lesson planning software application while their counterpart who specialized in OTM did not show a significant difference in that respect.

Table 5: Result of Post Hoc Tests (Descriptives) for Hypothesis One

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Accounting	5	.1867	.42531	.19020	-.3414	.7148	-.20	.87
Marketing	2	1.4000	.18856	.13333	-.2942	3.0942	1.27	1.53
OTM	4	.5333	.46508	.23254	-.2067	1.2734	.13	1.00
Total	11	.5333	.59255	.17866	.1353	.9314	-.20	1.53

(Source: Field Study, 2022)

As indicated in Table 5, business education lecturers who specialized in marketing with a mean score of 1.40 have the highest mean score than their counterpart who specialized in accounting and OTM with a mean score of 0.19 and 0.53 respectively.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson presentation software applications among business education lecturers based on their specialization.

Table 6: One-way ANOVA for Mean Difference among Business Education Lecturers on the Competency Training Needs in the use of Lesson Presentation Software Applications

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1.035	2	.518	2.858	.116	Accept
Within Groups	1.450	8	.181			
Total	2.485	10				

(Source: Field Study, 2022)

As indicated in Table 6, the result of the ANOVA shows that the p-value (0.12) is greater than the alpha value (0.05), therefore, the null hypotheses two is hereby accepted, this means that significant difference does not exist on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson presentation software applications among business education lecturers who specialized in accounting, marketing and office technology management.

Discussion of the Results

The result of research question one indicated that training is needed among business education lecturers in the usage of lesson planning software application in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, the corresponding hypothesis revealed that significant difference exists on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson planning software applications among business education lecturers based on their specialization. The result is in agreement with that of Onajite and Aina (2017) who found that business education lecturers in colleges of education need training in the preparation of lesson plans using computer system, the result also supports that of Ardic and Ciftci (2019) who reported that teachers need training in the use of ITCs. The result is in conformity with that of Anaza (2019) who concluded that student-teachers in colleges of education need training in the use of software applications. The result is in tandem with that of Dlamini and Mbatha (2018) who revealed that teachers need professional development (training) in the use of ICT in teaching.

The result of research question two indicated that training is needed among business education lecturers in the usage of lesson presentation software application in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, the corresponding hypothesis revealed that significant difference does not exist on the competency training needs in the usage of lesson presentation software applications among business education lecturers based on their specialization. The result is in line with the finding of Rizal et al., (2019) who reported that preservice science teachers need training in content creation including electronic presentation using presentation software applications. The result is supporting that of Timya et al., (2019) who revealed that OTM teachers highly need technology skills in the use of interactive multimedia package and web 2.0 tools. The result also conforms with the finding of Onajite and Aina (2017) who reported that business education lecturers in colleges of education need training in using PowerPoint presentation software. The result also agrees with that of Duktur (2019) who’s finding shows that business education undergraduate students need training in the use of PowerPoint presentation software. Among the studies that support this result include; Beaulieu and Poyo (2021) as well as Hassan and Mirza (2021).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the pilot study, it was concluded that the instrument's sub-scales for measuring the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson planning and lesson presentation software applications were found to be reliable and acceptable for the main study.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study and the conclusion reached, it was therefore recommended that:

- i. The instrument's sub-scale for measuring the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson planning software application should be used for the main study since it is found to be reliable and acceptable.
- ii. The instrument's sub-scale for measuring the competency training needs of business education lecturers in the usage of lesson presentation software application should be used for the main study since it is found to be reliable and acceptable.

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